

1 Combining quantitative and qualitative models to identify functional groups for
2 monitoring changes in the Bay of Biscay continental shelf exploited food web

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16 Abstract

17 To develop and implement ecosystem based management, it is critical to monitor food web
18 components or functional groups which are robust to uncertainty in ecosystem structure and
19 functioning yet sensitive to changes. To select such functional groups for the Bay of Biscay
20 continental shelf, both quantitative and qualitative food web models were developed. First,
21 functional groups for which predictions of directions of change following an increase in
22 primary productivity, prey or predators, or in fishing activities were identical across
23 alternative qualitative model structures were identified. Second, the robustness to model type
24 was assessed by comparing qualitative predictions with quantitative Ecopath model results.
25 The demersal fish community was identified as a sensitive and robust indicator for monitoring
26 food web ecological status in the Bay of Biscay. The present study also suggested potential
27 antagonistic effects of alternative management measures on small pelagic fish and highlighted
28 the need for joint management of all pressures.

29 Keywords: food web; comparative studies; ecosystem management; northeast Atlantic
30 continental shelf; loop analysis.

31

32 1. Introduction

33 Human activities increasingly affect ecosystem processes (Millenium Ecosystem Assessment,
34 2005). Therefore the ability to predict the direct and indirect effects of human activities has
35 become a priority (Jennings and Kaiser, 1998; Stevens *et al.*, 2000). For marine ecosystems,
36 implementing the ecosystem approach to fisheries, also called ecosystem-based fisheries
37 management (EBFM), has led to the development of a wide range of models dealing with
38 fishing effects at ecosystem scale (Plagànyi, 2007). Ecosystem models that take into account
39 several trophic levels are proposed as complements to conventional stock-assessment models,
40 for example, for refining estimates of mortality and production of commercially important
41 species (Gaichas *et al.*, 2010), or in a more holistic way, for providing information on the
42 state of the whole system (Baltic Sea case study; ICES (2011b)). In parallel to the
43 development of the ecosystem approach to fisheries, the European marine strategy framework
44 directive (MSFD) provides a legislative and operational framework at the European scale.
45 The main objective of the MSFD is to achieve or maintain “good environmental status”
46 (GES) of marine ecosystems by 2020 at the latest (<http://ec.europa.eu>; Directive 2008/56/EC).
47 Due to the complexity of ecosystems and their inherent spatial and temporal variability,
48 model predictions based on a single model structure are highly uncertain. As marine food
49 webs are difficult and costly to observe, variable amounts of information are gathered on
50 different parts of them, leading to uncertainty in data and subsequently in model parameter
51 estimates (Plagànyi and Butterworth, 2004; Hill *et al.*, 2007). The effects of model structure
52 and parameter uncertainty can be considerably reduced by considering predictions from a
53 suite of models of differing complexity; the approach is known as the “biological ensemble
54 modelling approach, BEMA” (Gårdmark *et al.*, 2012).
55 Quantitative predictions of the magnitude of food web responses to natural perturbations or
56 potential management measures are not always needed for management (Dambacher *et al.*,

57 2009). Instead, knowledge on directions of trends in food web components (Rochet *et al.*,
58 2010) and robust predictions from complementary models (Ortiz and Wolff, 2008; Metcalf,
59 2010) may be sufficient. In this study, robust model predictions are defined as those which are
60 similar for different models. If a number of alternative plausible models with different
61 structures and/or underlying functions and behaviours yield qualitatively similar predictions,
62 this helps to gauge how much confidence can be placed in the predictions and provides a basis
63 for selecting suitable management measures (Plagànyi and Butterworth, 2012). For the
64 implementation of the MSFD, the GES of ecosystems should be translated into measurable
65 environmental targets and associated indicators that can be monitored *in situ* in a cost-
66 effective manner (Van Hoey *et al.*, 2010). In this context, a multiple comparative modelling
67 approach could be useful for identifying reliable indicators of ecosystem changes (Samhuri
68 *et al.*, 2009; Metcalf *et al.*, 2011).

69 In marine ecosystems worldwide, continental shelves and slopes are subject to both land-
70 driven and marine anthropogenic pressures (Halpern *et al.*, 2008). The North-Eastern Atlantic
71 shelf was identified by Halpern and collaborators as one of the areas suffering from high
72 anthropogenic pressures. In the Bay of Biscay, fishing is the only human activity having
73 widespread documented impacts on several ecosystem components (Lorance *et al.*, 2009).
74 The present study used qualitative and quantitative food web models of the Bay of Biscay
75 continental shelf ecosystem to predict the effects of two kinds of human and natural pressure
76 changes: (i) increase in fishing pressure exerted by the different fleets operating in the area
77 and, (ii) increase in primary productivity due to nutrient inputs and/or climate change. The
78 main aims of the study were first to determine predicted ecosystem changes which were
79 robust to model structure, i.e. identical for alternative qualitative models, and to model type
80 (qualitative or quantitative models), and second to identify potential indicators for food web

81 ecological status monitoring which are robust to model uncertainty but sensitive to changes in
82 primary productivity or fishing pressure.

83 The paper is structured as follows. First, the two modelling approaches and the “Bay of
84 Biscay” models are presented. Second, the methodology used to determine sensitive food web
85 components are described. Third, a short description of Ecopath outputs is provided, followed
86 by the identification of predictions robust to both model structure and model type. Lastly, the
87 identification of suitable indicators of food web changes and management options that
88 emerged from this study is discussed. The focus was generally on small pelagics given their
89 large variability on an annual and decadal time scales and their role as a major natural
90 resource and as key contributors to the functioning of marine ecosystems (see the review by
91 Fréon *et al.* (2005)).

92

93 2. Material and Methods

94 2.1. Study area

95 The Bay of Biscay is a large gulf in the Northeast Atlantic located off the western coast of
96 France and the northern coast of Spain, between 48°5 and 43°5'N and 8 and 3'W (Figure 1).
97 It is part of the “Celtic-Biscay shelf” large marine ecosystem (LME;
98 <http://www.lme.noaa.gov/>). The Bay of Biscay supports a multi-species, multi-fleet fishery
99 with a large diversity of species exploited by a wide range of fishing gears primarily operated
100 from French and Spanish ports. The French fleets can be characterized by 12 landing profiles
101 each dominated by one or two species (Daurès *et al.*, 2009). Nine species characterized most
102 profiles and 20 species contributed over 80% in volume and value of French landings during
103 the period 2000 to 2006 (Daurès *et al.*, 2009). For the Spanish fleet, no equivalent information
104 was found. Though French fleet capacity has decreased over the last two decades, the positive
105 effects of this on the ecosystem are not (yet) detectable (Rochet *et al.*, 2012).

106

107 2.2. Quantitative modelling

108 2.2.1. Ecopath approach

109 The food web of the French continental shelf was modelled using Ecopath with Ecosim
110 (Christensen and Walters, 2004; Christensen *et al.*, 2008). EwE is a tool to analyse organic
111 matter and energy flows within a steady-state/static (Ecopath) and dynamic (Ecosim) mass-
112 balance model. The Ecopath model parameterization is based on two “master” equations. The
113 first equation decomposes the production term of each compartment (species or group of
114 species with similar trophic role):

115 Production = fishery catch + predation mortality + net migration + biomass accumulation +
116 other mortality

117 “Other mortality” includes natural mortality factors such as mortality due to senescence,
118 diseases, etc.

119 The second equation describes the energy balance within each group:

120 Consumption = production + respiration + unassimilated food

121 More formally, the two equations can be written as follows for group i and its predator j :

$$122 B_i \times (P/B)_i = Y_i + \sum_j (B_j \times (Q/B)_j \times DC_{ij}) + Ex_i + Bacc_i + B_i(1 - EE_i) \times (P/B)_i \quad (1)$$

123 and

$$124 B_i \times (Q/B)_i = B_i \times (P/B)_i + R_i + U_i \quad (2)$$

125 where the main input parameters are biomass density (B , here in $\text{kg C} \cdot \text{km}^{-2}$), production rate
126 (P/B , year^{-1}), consumption rate (Q/B , year^{-1}), proportion of i in the diet of j (DC_{ij} ; DC = diet
127 composition), net migration rate (Ex , year^{-1}), biomass accumulation ($Bacc$, year^{-1}), total catch
128 (Y ; $\text{kg C} \cdot \text{km}^{-2}$), respiration (R ; $\text{kg C} \cdot \text{km}^{-2} \cdot \text{year}^{-1}$), unassimilated food fraction (U) and
129 ecotrophic efficiency (EE).

130 Several indices can be derived from an Ecopath model. Niche overlap is calculated as the
131 proportion of prey and predators shared among different functional groups. Niche overlap
132 between two groups was assumed important if greater than 0.6. The mixed trophic impact
133 (MTI) matrix quantifies the direct and indirect trophic impacts of each functional group on
134 (the biomass of) all other functional groups (Ulanowicz and Puccia, 1990). It is calculated as
135 the product of all net impacts. The MTI is based on the assumption that the overall trophic
136 structure remains constant. The net impact of i on j , denoted q_{ij} , is given by the difference
137 between positive effects d_{ji} (quantified by the fraction of prey i in the diet of predator j), and
138 negative effects f_{ij} (evaluated as the fraction of total consumption of j used by predator i):

$$139 \quad q_{ij} = d_{ji} - f_{ij} \quad (3)$$

140 The elements of the MTI matrix m_{ij} are then calculated as the product of the net impacts q_{ij} of
141 all possible pathways in the food web that link the functional groups i and j . Negative m_{ij}
142 values indicate prevalence of predator effects (top-down effects) while positive values
143 indicate prevalence of prey effects (bottom-up effects). To evaluate the sensitivity of the signs
144 of the m_{ij} values (referred to as the original MTI values) to small changes in the q_{ij} values,
145 5000 Q matrices were created by drawing q_{ij} values from independent uniform distributions
146 defined by original $q_{ij} \pm 0.1$. The sample of Q matrices was then used to calculate m_{ij} values,
147 record their sign and estimate the percentage of m_{ij} values with the same sign as in the original
148 MTI matrix (S_{MTI}) (Rochette *et al.*, 2009; Nelva Pasqual, 2013). This sensitivity analysis is
149 not part of the distributed EwE 6 software package; further technical information can be
150 found in Rochette *et al.* (2009) and be requested from the first author.

151

152 2.2.2. Quantitative Bay of Biscay model

153 A full description of the Bay of Biscay Ecopath implementation, including the diet
154 composition and parameter values, can be found in Lassalle *et al.* (2011). For Ecopath results

155 to be meaningful, model parameters need to be based on information specific to the study
156 area. For almost all groups, biomass (B), production/biomass ratio (P/B),
157 consumption/biomass ratio (Q/B) as well as diet composition (DC) were derived from area
158 and period specific raw data or stock assessment results. Thirty-two functional groups were
159 included in the model: two seabirds groups, five marine mammal, nine fish, eight
160 invertebrate, three zooplankton, two primary producer, and one bacteria group, as well as
161 discards from commercial fisheries and pelagic detritus. The five main pelagic forage fish
162 species were given their own group while demersal fish were divided into four multi-species
163 groups on the basis of their diets. The model covered the central shelf of ICES divisions VIIIa
164 and b between the 30-m and 150-m isobaths with a surface area of 102 585 km². Shallower
165 and deeper parts were excluded for data availability reasons. The study area represented the
166 core of the distribution range for most species included in the model. Nevertheless, those
167 species were known to frequent the whole Northeast Atlantic (www.fishbase.org/). The model
168 represented a typical year between 1994 and 2005, i.e. before the collapse of the European
169 anchovy and the subsequent five-year closure of the fishery for this species.

170 The single fishery described in the original model by Lassalle *et al.* (2011) was split into three
171 fleets targeting small pelagic fish, demersal fish and invertebrates respectively to be able to
172 study the impacts of these fleets separately (Table 1). Regarding the main target species,
173 anchovy and sardine were mainly captured by offshore pelagic trawlers and coastal seiners
174 respectively, hake by offshore netters, sole by netters and *Nephrops* by trawlers, both
175 operating from coastal to more offshore waters (Daurès *et al.*, 2009). Due to these changes in
176 model structure, the model needed re-balancing, i.e. ecotrophic efficiency of piscivorous
177 demersal fish and carnivorous invertebrates' compartments were slightly above one. Their
178 biomasses were therefore increased by 4 and 10% respectively.

179 For parameterizing the three fishing fleets, for assessed stocks, international landings for
180 divisions VIIIa and b were obtained from reports of the relevant ICES working groups (see
181 Lassalle *et al.* (2011) for references). For multi-species fish groups, as well as mackerel and
182 horse mackerel, landings were taken from the Eurostat/ICES catch database (ICES 2010 -
183 Copenhagen). Annual landings were averaged over the period 1998-2003 for all
184 compartments as most of the biomass data were gathered during this interval (see
185 supplementary material 2 in Lassalle *et al.* (2011)). Due to lack of detailed spatial
186 information, landings could not be limited to the central shelf area, so they might be
187 somewhat overestimated.

188 Discards for each fishing fleet were obtained from the OBSMER programme for the year
189 2010 (Fauconnet *et al.*, 2011), stock assessment reports cited above and the scientific
190 literature (Pierce *et al.*, 2010). For this, based on expert advice (L. Fauconnet, pers. comm.),
191 each fishing gear was uniquely assigned to one of the three modelled fishing fleets (demersal,
192 pelagic and invertebrates). Due to sparse discard sampling coverage (mostly 2010), observer
193 bias, and non-random trip selection on a voluntary basis, discard estimates included in the
194 present model should be considered as the best estimates available, though they are most
195 likely underestimates.

196 Bycatch estimates for common dolphin and harbour porpoise were derived from observations
197 of incidental captures of cetaceans and seabirds in European waters (data from national
198 reports on the implementation of Regulation 812/2004); they were entered as discards in the
199 model. These recent cetacean bycatch estimates and past scientific publications indicated that
200 pelagic trawls were primarily responsible for common dolphins bycatch and set nets for
201 harbour porpoises incidental captures (see Lassalle *et al.* (2012) for references). Hence, the
202 estimates were assigned to the pelagic and demersal fleet respectively.

203

204 2.3. Qualitative modelling

205 2.3.1. Loop analysis

206 For qualitative system analysis, a food web can be represented by a graph, known as a signed
207 digraph (Levins, 1974), which displays the interactions between variables (here functional
208 groups and fleets) and is constructed using the signs of interactions (+, -, 0), not their
209 magnitude. This means model parameter values are not specified, only their signs. A signed
210 digraph has an equivalent representation in the community matrix (A) where each element a_{ij}
211 represents the direct effect of variable j on variable i . For instance, the direct effect of a
212 predator group on its prey, i.e. removal of biomass through predation, is represented by a
213 negative link, and the direct effect of a prey group on its predators, i.e. biomass creation,
214 gives rise to a positive link. Negative feedback connecting a population to it-self is termed a
215 self-effect. It represents intra-specific competition for space and resources particularly for
216 primary producers, intra-component predation, and links with the outside system as external
217 recruitment or consumption of species from outside the system (Puccia and Levins, 1985).
218 Dambacher (2001) showed that negative self-effects applied to all system components
219 promoted the stability of the system and the results of associate inverse community matrix.
220 Assuming the model system is at equilibrium, press perturbation analysis corresponds to
221 investigating the expected direction of change (toward a new equilibrium) of each model
222 variable, i.e. its abundance change, following sustained changes in the dynamics (birth or
223 death rates) of one or more model variables. It is carried out by considering the signs of the
224 adjoint of the negative community matrix ($\text{adj}-A$) (Dambacher *et al.*, 2002). In complex
225 systems, a press perturbation may impact a given variable through multiple pathways, a
226 pathway being a suite of direct (e.g. prey and predator) and indirect (e.g. prey of prey) effects
227 that lead from the input (pressed) variable to the response variable. If multiple pathways exist,
228 the resulting responses of a given variable may have opposing signs (increase, +, or decrease,

229 - in abundance). The opposing signs create ambiguity in the predicted responses to change
230 (Dambacher *et al.*, 2002). Weights can be given to the predictions to provide an assessment of
231 the level of ambiguity (Dambacher *et al.*, 2003). For a given response variable, the weight
232 corresponds to the net number of pathways (difference between the number of positive and
233 negative responses) divided by the total number of pathways. Weights range between 0
234 (complete sign indeterminacy of predictions; sign of overall effect will depend on interaction
235 strength) and 1 (sign completely determined).

236 For investigating model stability, the sign of all feedback loops in the system are inspected.
237 Negative feedback loops maintain a system's equilibrium. Conversely, positive feedbacks
238 magnify changes in variables and drive runaway growth or collapse (refer to Dambacher *et al.*
239 (2003) for a description of feedback cycles). A model system needs to be stable, at least under
240 certain conditions, for the results of press perturbation analyses to be meaningful.

241 PowerPlay (version 2.0; <http://esapubs.org/Archive/ecol/E083/022/suppl-1.htm>) was used to
242 draw signed digraph (Westfahl *et al.*, 2002) and the "Loop Analysis" facility provided on the
243 "Loop Group" web page (<http://www.ent.orst.edu/loop/>) to perform qualitative and symbolic
244 analysis of the community matrix, including press perturbation analyses corresponding to
245 changes in primary productivity and fishing mortality. For further details on loop analysis, see
246 Puccia and Levins (1985), Dambacher *et al.* (2002) and the web site of the "Loop Group".

247

248 2.3.2. Qualitative Bay of Biscay models

249 Rochet *et al.* (2013) proposed a simplified food web model for North-Atlantic temperate shelf
250 fish communities, that was adapted in the present study to the specific case of the Bay of
251 Biscay continental shelf (baseline model; Figure 2a). The model has seven functional groups
252 or model nodes which were organized into two trophic chains, one pelagic chain and one
253 benthic-demersal chain, coupled at different trophic levels and connected at the top by top

254 predators. Pelagic piscivores include albacore (*Thunnus alalunga*) and bluefin (*Thunnus*
255 *thynnus*) tunas which are highly migratory species caught off the shelf (but adjacent to the
256 shelf break) in the Bay of Biscay (international commission for the conservation of Atlantic
257 tunas (ICCAT); <http://www.iccat.es/en/>). As no reliable biomass estimates exist, pelagic
258 piscivores were not included in the Ecopath model. Tunas were assumed to have no impact on
259 pelagic planktivores given the low spatial and temporal overlap between these two groups.
260 Benthos includes suspension and deposit feeders of dead plankton bodies, but because
261 benthos is restricted to the sea floor, it is not expected to have a negative effect on living
262 plankton. Other predator-prey links (benefiting the predator and detrimental to the prey)
263 present in the original model of Rochet *et al.* (2013) were evaluated on the basis of the
264 expertise gained with the Bay of Biscay Ecopath model, which led to the removal of several
265 weak links. The modifications made to the original model of Rochet *et al.* (2013) were
266 summarized in Figure 2b (both additions and removals of links).
267 Fisheries were grouped into three fleets as in the Ecopath model: a pelagic fleet which targets
268 planktivores and pelagic piscivores, a demersal fleet targeting demersal piscivores,
269 benthivores are targeted and/or taken as bycatch by this fleet, and benthos is negatively
270 affected by the fishing gear. Some benthos species such as large crustaceans (e.g. Norway
271 lobster (*Nephrops norvegicus*)) were specifically targeted by an invertebrates fishery.
272 Press perturbation analyses were carried out for two general scenarios representing changes in
273 natural and anthropogenic pressures which correspond to a permanent increase or decrease in
274 (i) primary productivity resulting in higher/lower birth rates of each functional group, (ii) the
275 size of each fishing fleet due to fisheries management. As results of a permanent increase are
276 symmetrical (reverse in signs) to those for a permanent decrease, press perturbation results are
277 only presented for permanent increases.

278 The press perturbation of the baseline model and its three variants were compared to assess
279 structural uncertainty. The model variants were obtained by modifying some of the links in
280 the baseline model presented in Figure 2a. On the first hand, as the internal dynamics of a
281 fishery are more driven by management rather than by economics or resource state (Rochet *et*
282 *al.*, 2012), the positive links between targeted groups and fleets were removed from the
283 baseline model leading to the variant 1. On the other hand, the positive effect of demersal
284 benthivores on demersal piscivores was removed as it was questionable whether piscivores
285 population dynamics really depend on benthivores abundance. Variants 2 and 3 were thus
286 derived from the baseline model and the variant 1, respectively. Local conditions for stability
287 of the baseline model and its three variants were evaluated using two Routh-Hurwitz criteria
288 (Dambacher *et al.*, 2003).

289

290 2.4 Comparability of the qualitative and quantitative models

291 Studying potential system changes using loop analysis or the MTI matrix of an Ecopath
292 model both aim at taking into account direct (e.g. prey and predator) and indirect (e.g. prey of
293 prey) ecosystem interactions and depend on matrix algebra. Therefore, the results are often
294 interpreted in a similar way, that is as providing the likely system response to sustained small
295 positive or negative inputs (e.g. Metcalf (2010)). This interpretation was retained in the
296 present study but other alternatives exist (Nelva Pasqual, 2013). Metcalf (2010) asserted that
297 if model structure is the same when using MTI and qualitative modelling, and if no ambiguity
298 of flows or predictions occurs, the results obtained with the two methods will be of the same
299 sign. However, there is an important difference in the resolution at which the two model types
300 function the best and as such are generally constructed. A typical Ecopath model has between
301 24 and 40 functional groups, and should include at least 12 groups in order to cover the entire
302 ecosystem, from detritus to top predators (Christensen *et al.*, 2008). A qualitative model with

303 so many variables would provide highly ambiguous press perturbation results and thus bring
304 little insights into the dynamics of the system following perturbation. For example, weights of
305 most predictions were zero for a qualitative model with 35 functional groups as in the
306 Ecopath model. In contrast, in qualitative modelling, it is easy to use multiple simple model
307 structures and thus assess the effects of structural uncertainty on press perturbation results.
308 As Ecopath models with different number of groups can have different total impact matrices
309 in which the signs of relationships can be reversed, differences between MTI predictions and
310 press perturbation analyses should be interpreted with care (Nelva Pasqual, 2013). Briefly,
311 loop analysis is a qualitative analysis of the community matrix (Levins, 1974). Each element
312 of the community matrix represents the direct effect (+, -, 0) of one variable on the growth
313 rate of another variable at equilibrium (Puccia and Levins, 1985). In the case of MTI, the
314 direct impact matrix is calculated from flow transfers (Ulanowicz and Puccia, 1990).
315 Therefore, the community matrix and the MTI matrix can only be related when the flow
316 intensity reflects the strength of the dynamic effects between two variables. High flow
317 transfers can potentially be associated with a high dynamic effect, but it is not always the case
318 especially when considering interactions between populations.

319

320 2.5. Identifying functional groups sensitive to food web changes

321 Functional groups sensitive to natural or anthropogenic pressure changes are suitable as
322 indicators for monitoring changes in the food web dynamics. When identifying sensitive
323 functional groups, particular attention was paid to MTI and press perturbation results for
324 scenarios corresponding to an increase in fleets or a functional group, in particular plankton;
325 responses to a decrease are strictly reverse in signs. Indeed, in both approaches, the qualitative
326 nature of any indirect effect is determined by the sign of the product of the sequential actions
327 along the pathway by which such influence is exerted (Ulanowicz and Puccia, 1990). The

328 consequences of several perturbations happening concomitantly were not assessed as it
329 greatly increases model prediction ambiguity and such complex simulations (multiple
330 pressure scenarios) could not be performed using the available tools in Ecopath.
331 The identification of indicator functional groups was carried out in several steps. First,
332 qualitative (press perturbation) model predictions which had weighted predictions ≥ 0.5 and
333 were consistent over the baseline model and its three variants were selected. They were
334 termed robust qualitative predictions. Dambacher *et al.* (2002) had demonstrated that
335 weighted-prediction values >0.5 were found to exhibit high (near 95%) sign determinacy.
336 Second, their robustness to model type was investigated by comparing the qualitative
337 predictions to the niche overlap and MTI matrices from the Ecopath model. Further, the
338 predator and prey overlap indices were combined on the same graph to quantitatively identify
339 which species, or groups of species, were strongly linked by trophic interactions. Third,
340 functional groups (and species) with robust qualitative predictions and quantitative MTI
341 predictions with the same sign were identified. Fourth, among those groups, functional groups
342 which change (increase or decrease) when fleet size or another functional group is increased,
343 i.e. perturbed, were selected as suitable indicators of food web changes. They are three
344 important criteria for suitable ecosystem indicators: they should be sensitive to perturbations,
345 have an overall influence on the ecosystem and be currently monitored (Fulton *et al.*, 2005).
346 The modelling approach applied here ensures the first two criteria are fulfilled, the third
347 criteria is evaluated using additional information.

348

349 3. Results

350 3.1. Robust predictions determined from qualitative models

351 The baseline model and its three variants had local conditions for stability based on the
352 metrics of Dambacher *et al.* (2003). Press perturbation results for single pressure changes are

353 summarised in Table 2. The percentage of concordant predictions was low but allowed the
354 identification of robust conclusions which could be compared with the quantitative Ecopath
355 outputs. Most robust predictions corresponded to a top-down control exerted by higher
356 trophic level groups which was transmitted down the food web. Given the general structure of
357 the considered models, plankton (Plkt) was never influenced by any of the other functional
358 groups in any of the press perturbation analyses.

359 Regarding fishing activities, none of the qualitative predictions for an increase in the
360 invertebrate fleet (Inv Fleet) were consistent across alternative model structures. In contrast,
361 predictions regarding the impact of the pelagic fleet (Pel Fleet) presented high consistency in
362 terms of the groups impacted and the directions of responses. In all cases, the functional
363 group “top predators” (TopP) was predicted to decrease in abundance following a press
364 perturbation (increase) in the pelagic fleet. This decrease was associated with a concomitant
365 response of the demersal food chain, i.e. an increase of demersal piscivores and a decrease in
366 demersal benthivores. An increase in the demersal fleet (Dem Fleet) was always predicted to
367 lead to an increase of pelagic planktivores (Plv). Plv were predicted to also increase in
368 response to an increase in primary productivity (Plkt).

369 Permanent changes in top predators and demersal piscivores led to robust qualitative
370 predictions of changes for themselves and other functional groups. An increase in top
371 predators was predicted to have a negative effect on demersal piscivores and a positive one on
372 demersal benthivores. An increase in demersal piscivores was predicted to have a negative
373 impact on their benthic, demersal and pelagic prey, namely demersal benthivores and pelagic
374 planktivores.

375

376 3.2 Ecopath outputs

377 The combination of predator and prey diet overlap indices highlighted two groups occupying
378 the same trophic niche within the Bay of Biscay food web and as such being susceptible to
379 respond similarly or conjointly to perturbations. The two groups consist of the small pelagics
380 which have both similar prey and predators among the five species, and the suprabenthivorous
381 demersal fish which share a large part of their prey, and have the same predators (Figure 3a).
382 Considering the MTI of each functional group, the largest impacts were positive and due to
383 phytoplankton, mesozooplankton and detritus (Figure 3b). Among the three fishing fleets,
384 only the invertebrate fleet had a positive MTI. Discards, which were caused by the
385 invertebrate fleet, were predicted to induce a positive response of the system in the MTI
386 assessment as well. Top predators and demersal fish compartments presented a homogeneous
387 overall negative impact on the system while the effects of small pelagics differed. A small
388 increase of anchovy, sardine and sprat was predicted to provoke a positive response of the
389 food web as a whole, in contrast to a negative impact for mackerel and horse mackerel (Figure
390 3b).

391

392 3.3. Concordant predictions

393 Robust qualitative predictions were found to be largely but not always consistent with the
394 quantitative Ecopath outputs (Table 3). In the Ecopath model, suprabenthivorous demersal
395 fish shared the same predators with all five modelled forage fish species (predator overlap
396 index ≥ 0.8) (Figure 3a). This quantitative result was consistent with the predicted identical
397 qualitative response of Btv and Plv to an increase in demersal piscivores (Table 3). However,
398 when considering the MTI matrix, a negative impact of piscivorous demersal fish was
399 predicted only for prey pertaining to the benthic-demersal food chain, thus the equivalent of
400 Btv (Figure 4). S_{MTI} values ranged from 91 to 100 depending on the functional groups which
401 indicated that the signs of the MTI matrix were insensitive to small changes in net impacts.

402 The small pelagic species shared the highest percentage of common prey, mostly composed of
403 zooplankton (prey overlap index ≥ 0.75) (Figure 3a). A slight increase in large phytoplankton
404 was predicted by the MTI to result in a common positive response of all small pelagic species,
405 with the value of S_{MTI} being smallest for sprat (65%). This shared pattern was even clearer
406 when mesozooplankton was the impacting group (Figure 4), *i.e.* MTI values were higher and
407 sign stable (S_{MTI} 100%). These two quantitative results were in accordance with the robust
408 qualitative prediction of a positive response of the Plv group to a persistent increase of
409 primary production (Plkt) (Table 3).

410 Prey overlap was found to be high between seabirds, marine mammals and piscivorous
411 demersal fish. In the MTI it translated only into significant negative impacts between
412 bottlenose dolphins and piscivorous demersal fish which constituted the sole major effect of
413 top predators on the food web (Figure 4) (S_{MTI} 100%). As such, the Ecopath model was able
414 to take the analysis one step further in suggesting that the negative impact of top predators
415 (TopP) on Dpis identified through press perturbation analysis was more likely related to
416 competition for food resources rather than to predation, *i.e.* the two groups feed largely on the
417 same prey.

418 In contrast, quantitative and qualitative findings did not agree regarding a positive impact of
419 an increase of top predators for benthivores (Table 3). This was due to some extent to the diet
420 regime of top predators differing between the two modelling approaches. In the Ecopath
421 model, marine mammals were feeding on piscivorous and benthivorous, suprabenthivorous,
422 and benthivorous demersal fish. No such trophic link existed between TopP and Btv in the
423 qualitative baseline model (Figure 2a).

424 Common dolphins and harbour porpoises, which are bycaught by the pelagic and demersal
425 fleets respectively (Table 1), were predicted by the Ecopath model to be negatively (S_{MTI}
426 100%) impacted by a slight increase of fishing activities (Figure 4). Nevertheless, prey

427 overlap between top predators and fishing fleets was low to moderate (values ≥ 0.6 only for
428 common dolphins) and did not suggest strong competition between these two predator groups
429 for the same resources. Thus, the negative impacts were a result of direct effects of fishing.
430 These quantitative findings again strengthened the predictions obtained from the qualitative
431 models (Table 3).

432 Finally, conclusions derived from qualitative modelling regarding the impacts of the pelagic
433 fleet on functional groups in the benthic-demersal food chain and the effects of the demersal
434 fleet on zooplanktivorous pelagic fish were not confirmed by quantitative model outputs
435 (Table 3).

436

437 3.4 Potential indicators of food web changes

438 The predictions which were robust to model structure and model type concerned benthivores
439 (corresponding to several demersal fish compartments in the Ecopath model) and planktivores
440 (corresponding to anchovy, sardine, sprat, mackerel and horse mackerel in the Ecopath
441 model) (Table 3). Benthivores are predicted to decrease when their demersal piscivores
442 predators increase, while planktivores increase when primary productivity increases. Thus
443 benthivores and planktivores are potential indicator groups as together they are sensitive to
444 two types of food web changes, in the abundance of demersal piscivores and in primary
445 productivity, respectively.

446 Though all demersal fish had a negative MTI, the relative magnitude varied between Ecopath
447 demersal compartments (Figure 3b). The two groups with the strongest negative impact on the
448 ecosystem (MTI) were the suprabenthivorous demersal fish and the benthivorous and
449 piscivorous demersal fish (see supplementary material for their detailed composition). Blue
450 whiting (*Micromesistius poutassou*) represented 80% of the biomass of suprabenthivorous
451 demersal fish. Half of the biomass of benthivorous and piscivorous demersal fish was

452 composed of Gadidae, i.e. bib (*Trisopterus luscus*) and sand goby (*T. minutus*). The remaining
453 half comprised several other species.

454 Availability of survey data series is the third criteria for suitable indicator groups. In the Bay
455 of Biscay, a regular bottom trawl survey started in 1987, while pelagic planktivores have been
456 surveyed annually since 2000 using fisheries acoustics.

457

458 4. Discussion

459 In this study, benthivores and planktivores were identified as functional groups sensitive to
460 food web changes, independent of model structure and type. For planktivores, commonly
461 referred to as small pelagics, two robust predictions were identified: a high risk of decline
462 associated with an increase in demersal piscivorous fish abundance and a potential increase
463 following a rise in primary productivity, the reverse being also true. The first pressure change,
464 for which predictions were only partially robust to model type, is very likely to take place
465 during phases of demersal fish stock rebuilding, such as occurred in the recent years for the
466 European hake (*Merluccius merluccius*) stocks (ICES, 2011a). The European hake is an
467 abundant piscivorous species with a substantial part of its diet composed of small pelagics
468 (Guichet, 1995; Cabral and Murta, 2002; Le Loc'h, 2004). The second result is relevant in the
469 context of decreasing eutrophication in coastal areas, but also climate variability (Beaugrand
470 and Reid, 2003). A temporary or permanent diminution in system fertility and thus primary
471 production could follow and as such constrain to a certain degree the abundance of
472 zooplanktivorous fish populations (Malzahn *et al.*, 2007). In the Bay of Biscay, several
473 coastal areas with eutrophication problems have been identified (AAMP and Ifremer, 2011).
474 Recently, balanced harvesting, which is defined as applying fishing mortality in proportion to
475 natural productivity, has been advocated as a way to maintain relative size and species
476 compositions of exploited ecosystems (Garcia *et al.*, 2012). However, indirect effects might

477 complicate the picture. The qualitative model analyses results indicated that a given fishery
478 could affect the opposite food chain, e.g. pelagic fleets could change the abundance of
479 functional groups in the benthic-demersal food chain. This cross-effect is in line with the
480 findings of Rochet *et al.* (2013) regarding the way anthropogenic and natural pressures
481 propagate within food webs. Indeed, these authors stated that the multi-species fisheries
482 operating in the northeast Atlantic are characterised since decades by a low fishing selectivity
483 across and within functional groups. Using qualitative models, the same authors demonstrated
484 that these less selective fisheries might create antagonistic pressures, the impacts of which
485 being less predictable. Nevertheless, quantitative outputs of the present work (MTI and
486 overlap index) did not confirm propagation of fishing pressure. A possible explanation for this
487 discrepancy is that direct impacts of individual fishing fleets on their targeted stocks were not
488 strong and consequently indirect impacts on opposite food chain components were even less
489 detectable.

490 A four step approach was proposed in the present study to determine indicator functional
491 groups suitable to evaluate food web effects of pressure changes, particularly fishing. In a
492 previous study of the Bay of Biscay ecosystem, functional groups were also found to be a
493 relevant level at which to seek impacts of fishing pressures and other changes (Rochet *et al.*,
494 2010). The indicator groups of the current study being robust to model structure and type,
495 they can provide support for the definition of management options robust to model
496 uncertainty. However, multiple impacts were not analysed in the present work as they
497 increase ambiguity in qualitative predictions and are difficult to perform with EwE. However,
498 it should be acknowledged that applying several pressures concomitantly is an important step
499 in selecting and interpreting ecological indicators, particularly when ambiguities can be
500 overcome by accounting for the relative strength of positive and negative effects.

501 During the selection process of indicators suitable to describe GES under the European
502 MSFD, the “large fish indicator” (LFI) has been identified as an indicator of “food web”
503 structure (Rogers *et al.*, 2010) and was more particularly viewed as an indicator of the general
504 “health” of the demersal fish community (Greenstreet *et al.*, 2009). In the North Sea, LFI is
505 defined as the proportion by weight of fish greater than 40 cm in length and is notably
506 sensitive to variations in fishing pressure. Others have derived expected directions of changes
507 under the impact of fishing (Shin *et al.*, 2005), i.e. a decrease in the proportion of large fish
508 with increasing fishing pressure. However, concrete applications to demersal communities
509 have highlighted that the actual processes that link changes in the LFI to changes in fishing
510 pressure still remain to be properly understood (Rochet *et al.*, 2007; Greenstreet *et al.*, 2011;
511 Shephard *et al.*, 2011).

512 Propositions were made to convert the LFI index into an indicator of “food web” status
513 (MSFD descriptor 4) (Rombouts *et al.*, 2013): the use of species-specific thresholds to define
514 large individuals rather than a single cut-off point, e.g. 40 cm, and coupling of this indicator
515 with the maximum asymptotic length (L_{∞}) to take into account changes in species
516 composition. From this perspective, the two demersal compartments in the Ecopath model
517 with the greatest overall impact on the ecosystem corresponded to 48 species, among which
518 five dominated the biomass and included most of the evaluated stocks (see supplementary
519 material). This information could help to define the species to be included in the suite of
520 species to be monitored within the demersal fish functional groups in the Bay of Biscay
521 continental shelf ecosystem.

522 In conclusions, an easy-to-implement modelling approach combining two types of ecosystem
523 models was applied to draw robust conclusions regarding the functioning of the Bay of Biscay
524 continental shelf food web and its expected responses to single perturbations. The approach

525 offers a structured way towards the selection of indicators for monitoring food web status and
526 responses to perturbations.

527

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533

534 Supplementary material

535 Supplementary material is available at the ICESJMS online version of the paper. It includes
536 the species composition of the four demersal fish compartments in the Bay of Biscay
537 continental shelf ecosystem model.

538 Figure captions

539 Figure 1. Study area of the Bay of Biscay continental shelf and locations of the main rivers
540 flowing into it. The shaded area corresponded to the French part of the continental shelf. For
541 clarification, ICES divisions VIIIa and b are also added in bold line.

542

543 Figure 2. (a) Baseline qualitative model of the Bay of Biscay continental shelf food web.

544 System variables include trophic groups (circles) and fishing fleets (squares). Arrows

545 represent positive links, circles negative links. Closed circles starting and ending at the same

546 variable represent self-effect (density-dependence). TopP: Top Predators; Ppis: Pelagic

547 Piscivores; Plv: Pelagic Planktivores; Plkt: Plankton; Dpis: Demersal Piscivores; Btv:

548 Demersal Benthivores; Bthos: benthos; Dem fleet: Demersal fleet; Pel fleet: Pelagic fleet; Inv

549 fleet: Invertebrate fleet. Dashed links were those that were altered for creating model variants.

550 (b) Summary of modifications made to adapt the generic qualitative model proposed by

551 Rochet *et al.* (2013) to the Bay of Biscay case study. Added links are in bold and removed

552 links dashed.

553

554 Figure 3. (a) Prey versus predator niche overlap index derived from an Ecopath model.

555 Groups in the upper left corner have a very high overlap of prey; groups in the upper right

556 corner have a high overlap of both predators and prey. (b) Total mixed trophic impacts of

557 each functional group on the ecosystem (sum over the remaining groups). Compartments

558 were ordered by qualitative model groups, e.g. mackerel, horse mackerel, anchovy, sardine

559 and sprat pertained to the planktivorous fish category (Plv) and as such they were more

560 closely grouped together in the graph. The names corresponding to the numbers of functional

561 groups are given in Table 1. 33 pelagic fleet; 34 demersal fleet; 35 invertebrate fleet.

562

563 Figure 4. Combined direct and indirect trophic impacts that a functional group (impacting
564 group) had on each of the remaining groups (impacted groups) in the Ecopath model. Black
565 circles indicate potential positive impacts and white circles potential negative impacts.

566

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716

717

718 Table 1. Landings and discards (kg C·km⁻²·year⁻¹) of the three fishing fleets included in the Ecopath model of the continental shelf of the Bay of
 719 Biscay.

720	Pelagic fleet (Pel Fleet)		Demersal fleet (Dem Fleet)		Invertebrates fleet (Inv Fleet)	
721	<i>Y</i>	Discards	<i>Y</i>	Discards	<i>Y</i>	Discards
722						
723	1. Plunge and pursuit divers seabirds					
724	2. Surface feeders seabirds					
725	3. Striped dolphins <i>Stenella coeruleoalba</i>					
726	4. Bottlenose dolphins <i>Tursiops truncatus</i>					
727	5. Common dolphins <i>Delphinus delphis</i> 0.101*					
728	6. Long-finned pilot whale <i>Globicephala melas</i>					
729	7. Harbour porpoise <i>Phocoena phocoena</i> 0.0078*					
730			8.86	0.43	1.56	0.38
731	9. Piscivorous and benthivorous demersal fish	0.64	5.45	2.43	4.59	1.22
732	10. Suprabenthivorous demersal fish				0.64	26.79
733	11. Benthivorous demersal fish		4.63		0.37	
734	12. Mackerel <i>Scomber scombrus</i>	1.69 0.49	4.55	0.90		0.34
735	13. Horse mackerel <i>Trachurus trachurus</i> 15.13				1.68	
736	14. Anchovy <i>Engraulis encrasicolus</i> 16.80 0.10					
737	15. Sardine <i>Sardina pilchardus</i> 10.82					
738	16. Sprat <i>Sprattus sprattus</i>					
739	17. Benthic cephalopods		3.53			
740	18. Pelagic cephalopods		1.99			
741	19. Carnivorous benthic invertebrates			1.24	2.91	0.84
742	20. Necrophagous benthic invertebrates					
743	21. Sub-surface deposit feeders invertebrates					
744	22. Surface suspension and deposit feeders inv.					
745	23. Benthic meiofauna					
746	24. Suprabenthic invertebrates					
747	25. Macrozooplankton (≥ 2 mm)					

- 748 26. Mesozooplankton (0.2-2 mm)
 - 749 27. Microzooplankton (≤ 0.2 mm)
 - 750 28. Bacteria
 - 751 29. Large phytoplankton (≥ 3 μm)
 - 752 30. Small phytoplankton (< 3 μm)
 - 753 31. Discards
 - 754 32. Pelagic detritus
-

755 *Bycatch of toothed cetaceans (common dolphins and harbour porpoises).

756 Table 2. Expected directions of change* of the abundance of different functional groups and fishing fleets based on press perturbation analysis of
 757 Bay of Biscay continental shelf food web models. Only predictions which were consistent (same direction) across a baseline model and its three
 758 variants and had weights ≥ 0.5 were retained. Corresponding Ecopath compartment numbers from Table 1 are given in brackets. Blank cells
 759 indicate ambiguous predictions.

760 761 Impacted 762 group (Ecopath)	763 <u>Impacting group (increase)</u>									
	764 TopP	765 Ppis	766 Dpis	767 Plv	768 Btv	769 Plkt	770 Bthos	771 Dem fleet	772 Pel Fleet	773 Inv fleet
763 Top predators (1-7)	+							- [†]	-	
764 Pelagic piscivores										
765 Demersal piscivores (8)	-		+						+	
766 Planktivores (12-16)			-	+		+		+		
767 Benthivores (9-11)	+		-						-	
768 Plankton (25-27, 29, 30)	0	0	0	0	0		0	0	0	0
769 Benthos (19-24)										
770 Demersal fleet (33)								+		
771 Pelagic fleet (34)									+ [†]	
772 <u>Invertebrates fleet (35)</u>										

773 *+ (increase), - (decrease) or 0 (no trend) indicates the direction of the response in group *i* (impacted group in rows) resulting from a sustained
 774 positive input into group *j* (impacting groups in columns); e.g. the predicted response of a sustained increase in top predators is predicted to have
 775 a positive effect on demersal benthivorous fish.

776 [†] Signs vary with the inclusion (or not) of the positive effect of Btv on Dpis in model variants.

777 Table 3. Concordance between robust qualitative model predictions (press perturbation analyses in Table 2) and quantitative Ecopath outputs.

778 Ecopath outputs were compared with qualitative predictions in terms of ecosystem components impacted and directions of change.

779			
780	Robust qualitative predictions	Quantitative outputs	
781		Diet overlap	MTI
782	Increase in demersal piscivores (Dpis) has negative effect on their bentho-	Yes	Yes, only for demersal prey
783	demersal (Btv) and pelagic prey (Plv).		
784	Increase in primary productivity (Plkt) has positive effect on Plv.	Yes	Yes
785	Increase in top predators (TopP) has negative effect on Dpis	Yes	Yes, only bottlenose dolphins
786	and positive effect on Btv		No
787	Increase in Pel Fleet has negative effect on TopP and	Yes*	Yes, on common dolphins
788	Btv and positive effect on Dpis	No*	No
789	<u>Increase in Dem Fleet has positive effect on Plv</u>	No	No

790 *Prey overlap indices between ecosystem components and pelagic fishery were calculated using the modified Pianka index proposed in Ecopath

791 which is based on proportions of the different prey consumed: pursuit diver seabirds (0.64), common dolphins (0.73) and piscivorous demersal

792 fish (0.66).